

Financial Risk and Financial Performance of Tier 3 Commercial Banks in Kenya

Sylvia Mbithe Wambua

*PhD Scholar (Business Administration-Finance),
Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya*

Prof. Gregory Simiyu Namusonge, PhD

Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya

Prof. Romanus Odhiambo, PhD

Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya

Suggested Citation

Wambua, S.M., Namusonge, G.S., & Odhiambo, R. (2025). Financial Risk and Financial Performance of Tier 3 Commercial Banks in Kenya. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 261-272.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(1\).25](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(1).25)

Abstract:

Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya play a vital role in the country's economic growth by facilitating the supply of money and supporting economic ventures. However, these banks face significant challenges that affect their financial performance, with financial risk being a critical factor. Financial risk involves potential losses arising from inadequate revenue generation, operational failures, market volatility, or regulatory changes, and primarily manifests in credit, market, operational, and liquidity risks. The objective of the study was to assess the influence of financial risk on the financial performance of

Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya, with a focus on the moderating role of bank size. A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted, targeting branch managers, executive managers, finance managers, credit managers, and other key personnel from Tier 3 banks. Data collection involved questionnaires for primary data and a secondary data collection sheet for financial performance metrics, analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study found that financial risk negatively affects financial performance, highlighting the need for effective risk management strategies. To mitigate financial risks, Tier 3 banks should implement robust risk-rating systems, continuous monitoring frameworks, and leverage financial innovations such as advanced analytics and digital tools to enhance decision-making. Strengthened internal controls, balanced loan portfolios, and adherence to prudential guidelines were also recommended to improve financial performance. Additionally, the study emphasized the importance of bank size as a moderating factor, underscoring the need for strategies aligned with the scale of operations. Future research could explore sector-specific risks and the role of emerging financial technologies in risk management for more granular insights.

Keywords: *Financial Risks, Financial Performance, Tier 3 Commercial Banks.*

Introduction

The banking sector plays a crucial role in the performance of a country's economy, with commercial banks being instrumental in

executing monetary policies and providing payment facilitation for goods and services. Acting as intermediaries, banks mobilize and direct resources from surplus areas to deficit regions in the economy (Klein & Mayer, 2016).

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

In Kenya, the liberalization of the banking sector in the early 1990s intensified competition, prompting financial institutions to expand into rural areas (Ouma, Odongo, & Were, 2017). Due to globalization, commercial banks have diversified their operations to capture market share in both developed and emerging economies (Kanika, 2012). Technology-driven financial innovation has further extended banking services, enabling secure, low-cost mobile financial services that increase financial inclusion, as seen in Tanzania, where 79% of the population uses mobile banking (Ishengoma, 2011).

Despite these advancements, financial risks remain a significant challenge for commercial banks, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where financial exclusion is prevalent (Mutsonziwa & Maposa, 2016). Financial risks, including credit risk, market risk, operational risk, and liquidity risk, can undermine the ability of banks to provide consistent services and affect their financial stability and performance. In 2011, financial exclusion was evidenced by only 42% of Kenyans having formal accounts, compared to 30% in Nigeria and 10% in Egypt (World Bank, 2011). In Kenya, financial risks have hindered efforts to enhance financial inclusion, especially in rural areas, where a large portion of the population remains unbanked (Bansal, 2014). Additionally, the rise of foreign banks in sub-Saharan Africa has introduced competitive pressures, adversely impacting the performance of domestic banks, which often face higher exposure to financial risks due to limited resources and infrastructure (Claessens & Hore, 2012).

The Kenyan government has implemented measures to encourage financial inclusion by fostering the development of commercial banking services and addressing financial risks. These efforts have led to a significant increase in formal financial service usage, tripling between 2006 and 2015 (Muteti, 2014). However, mitigating financial risks remains critical to sustaining this growth. Robust risk management frameworks, prudent lending practices, and continuous monitoring of financial innovations

are essential for balancing inclusion efforts and maintaining financial stability.

Statement of the Problem

The banking sector is integral to global and national economies, facilitating resource mobilization and enabling efficient economic transactions (World Bank, 2017). In Kenya, the liberalization of the banking sector in the 1990s introduced intense competition, significantly affecting financial performance, especially for Tier 3 commercial banks, which control only 8.98% of the market share (CBK, 2016). These banks face unique challenges, including limited assets, constrained lending limits, and exposure to financial risks such as credit, market, operational, and liquidity risks. These risks have been linked to their underperformance, with Tier 3 banks collectively posting a 2.2% decline in pre-tax profits between 2015 and 2016, attributed to high non-performing loans and weak governance structures (CBK, 2017).

Notably, Dubai Bank and Imperial Bank were placed under receivership during this period due to inadequate capital, liquidity challenges, and poor governance, while Jamii Bora Bank reported losses of Ksh 490 million, and Consolidated Bank Ksh 277 million (CBK, 2016). Financial risks significantly influence Tier 3 banks' financial performance, with high-risk exposures undermining profitability and stability. For example, high non-performing loans erode revenue streams, while inadequate liquidity compromises their ability to meet short-term obligations (Grenade, 2014).

To mitigate these risks, Tier 3 banks must strengthen internal controls, implement robust risk management frameworks, and comply with Central Bank of Kenya guidelines. Improved governance and adherence to prudential regulations can reduce vulnerability to financial shocks and enhance stability. Addressing financial risks is critical for improving the financial performance of Tier 3 banks and ensuring their continued contribution to Kenya's economy (Gichinga, 2016).

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to evaluate the influence of financial risk on financial performance of Tier 3 Commercial Banks in Kenya.

Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypothesis:

H_{01} : There is no significant influence of financial risks on financial performance of Tier 3 Commercial Banks in Kenya.

Theoretical Review

The application of risk management theory, developed by David (1997), is highly relevant to understanding the influence of financial risks on the performance of Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya. This theory underscores the necessity of risk management, particularly in addressing market and credit risks, which are central to the challenges faced by Tier 3 banks. Market risk, driven by changes in interest rates, exchange rates, equity prices, and commodity prices, can significantly impact a bank's financial stability by altering the net value of its assets (Wu & Olson, 2010). Similarly, credit risk, arising from non-performing loans, poses a substantial threat to the profitability and survival of these banks.

Regulators and bank managers must consider the total risk rather than just the individual risk components of a portfolio, as per Markowitz's portfolio theory. This is critical for Tier 3 banks, which often lack the scale to absorb significant losses and are more susceptible to financial shocks. The necessity of robust risk measurement tools like Value at Risk (VAR) is highlighted in this context. VAR enables banks to estimate potential losses under adverse market conditions by analyzing asset return dispersion. Its computational efficiency and ability to account for market structures make it suitable for evaluating market risk in Tier 3 banks, which must navigate limited resources and heightened competition (Muhammad & Bilal, 2014).

The theory also emphasizes the trade-off between risk precision and cost, which is pertinent for Tier 3 banks operating under

constrained financial and operational capacities. Scenario analysis and VAR are complementary tools for quantifying risks, with scenario analysis offering a subjective view of potential outcomes and VAR providing a quantitative assessment based on historical data (Sovan, 2009). By employing these tools, Tier 3 banks can identify maximum potential losses and align their capital reserves accordingly, ensuring regulatory compliance and enhancing their ability to withstand financial shocks.

In this study, VAR was applied to quantify market risk, reflecting the theoretical foundation of risk management. This aligns with the need for Tier 3 banks to adopt systematic approaches to measure and mitigate risks, ensuring their financial performance remains stable amid volatility. Strengthening risk management frameworks based on these theoretical insights can enhance Tier 3 banks' resilience and contribute to their long-term sustainability.

Literature Review

Financial risk, traditionally associated with portfolio variance, can stem from external or internal factors. External financial risks arise from changes in financial markets, while internal financial risks originate from the organization itself (Eichhorn, 2004). The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM), as described by Engle (2004), demonstrates the relationship between expected returns and variance when all investors follow the same objectives and information. While traditional methods such as Value-at-Risk (VaR) effectively quantify potential short-term losses, they fall short in addressing intra-horizon risks that may lead to cascading problems like early liquidation or margin calls (Yen & Lin, 2008). Modern risk measurement methodologies like the GARCH models, an extension of ARCH, are now widely used to capture dynamic volatilities, fat tails, and volatility clustering in financial markets (Parke & Waters, 2007; Bakshi & Panayotov, 2010).

Empirical studies have provided insights into the impact of financial risks on organizational performance. Nyasaka (2017) demonstrated that

The results in Table 1 showed that mean of the financial risk was 3.7744 while the median was 3.8333. The results indicated that there was a range in the financial risk of 1.56 with a minimum value of 2.67 and a maximum of 4.22 for the Tier 3 commercial banks. This is supported by Kihuro (2018) carried a research on Credit Risk Management and Bank Performance, the findings established that a weak credit risk management systems may lead to higher non-performing loans and ultimately negatively impact on the bank performance, the research recommended that it's important to incorporate the emerging new ICT supported tools in improving the credit risk management systems and test the impact of improved credit assessment models as well as the revamped credit information platforms such as the Credit Reference Bureaus (CRBs). However, the research did not factor in the impact of the external forces such as macroeconomic factors on the relationship between the NPLs and the bank performance.

Bank Size

Bank Size was a moderating factor which was used to establish the influence on the relationship between the predictor variables and financial performance of Tier 3 Commercial Banks in Kenya. The descriptive statistical findings are indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Bank Size Descriptive Statistics

Mean	2.4886
Median	2.3750
Standard Deviation	0.5057
Range	2.19
Minimum	1.38
Maximum	3.56
Observation	99

The results showed that mean of the bank Size was 2.4886 while the median was 2.3750. The results indicated that there was a range in the bank Size of 2.19. The minimum value was 1.38 while the maximum value was 3.56 for the Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya. Amoh,(2017) study included the moderating effects of the bank size and the findings indicated that bank

size moderates the effect internal controls on financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya by shrinking it Further its supported by a study of Marinković and Radović, (2014) who argued that customer profile can be affected by the bank size bank as large banking firms enjoy a competitive advantage over small banking firms as larger firm can lend to large customers. This advantage stems from the ability of large banks to exploit the economies of scale in making evaluations on hard information available on this kind of customers. Small banks lack the capacity to lend to large customers. These small banks have a challenge as they are constrained in terms of lending limits as guided by the regulator. The most commonly used measures of the size of a bank is total assets, market share and customer Deposit.

Financial Performance

Financial Performance was the dependent variables researched for Tier 3 commercial banks in this study. The descriptive statistical findings are indicated in Table 3.

Table 3. Financial Performance Descriptive Statistics

Mean	702.424
Median	116.000
Standard Deviation	2139.715
Range	9092.000
Skewness	2.362
Minimum	-1576.00
Maximum	7516.000
Observation	99

The results showed that mean of the financial performance was 702.424 while the median was 116.000. The results indicated that there was a wide range in the financial performance of 9092. This implied that there was wide disparity in the profit of these Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya with a minimum value of profit being a loss of 1576 and a maximum profit of 7516. Skewness of 2.362 was accepted considering that a value between -3.0 to +3.0 is acceptable. This is supported by the fact that over the last few years, the banking sector has shown robust growth. However, when analyzed by tier classification, it

was established that the pre-tax profits of tier three commercial banks decreased by 2.2% during the period 2015 to 2016. This decline was attributed to five commercial banks in this category posting losses. First community bank realized a loss of Kshs. 41.0 million, Jamii Bora Bank realized a loss of Ksh.490.0 million, and Consolidated Bank realized a loss of Kshs. 277.0 million (CBK2016;2017)

Hypothesis Testing

A regression analysis of the effect of financial risks on financing performance of Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya was carried out. The linear regression model for internal controls results is presented in Table 4.

The regression equation based on the provided results is as follows:

$$\text{Financial Performance} = -1347.23 + 543.04 \cdot \text{Financial Risks} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- -1347.23 is the constant (intercept), representing the baseline financial performance when financial risks are zero.
- 543.04 is the coefficient for financial risks, indicating the expected change in financial performance for a one-unit increase in financial risks.

The insignificant p-value (0.423) suggests that the coefficient for financial risks is not statistically significant, meaning the relationship may not be meaningful in practice.

Table 4. Regression Results for Financial Risks and Financial Performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Sig. Change	F
1	0.081 ^a	0.007	-0.004	2143.58	0.007	0.647	0.423	

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2974053	1	0.647	0.423 ^b
	Residual	445707083	97		
	Total	448681136	98		

Regression Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-1347.23	2556.8		-0.527	0.599
	FinRisks	543.04	674.9	0.081	0.805	0.423

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance; b. Predictors: (Constant), FinRisks

The regression analysis indicates a weak and statistically insignificant relationship between financial risks and financial performance in Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya. With an R-value of 0.081, the correlation between the two variables is minimal. The R-Square value of 0.007 shows that financial risks account for only 0.7% of the variation in financial performance, while the adjusted R-Square suggests the model fails to explain the variance effectively. The ANOVA results confirm the model's lack of statistical significance, as the F-statistic (0.647) has a p-value of 0.423, exceeding the 0.05

threshold. Additionally, the regression coefficient for financial risks (543.04) is positive but statistically insignificant ($p = 0.423$), suggesting the observed effect may be due to random chance rather than a genuine relationship. This is in-line with Nyasaka (2017) who carried out a study on management of credit risk and non-performing loans in the banks. In his study, credit risk was measured by the characteristic of the borrower which was used to determine the credit score. The study noted that non-performing loans negatively affected a bank's lending ability. This created a negative

signaling effect on credit risk

These findings imply that financial risks, as analyzed in this study, do not significantly influence financial performance, highlighting the potential dominance of other factors like operational efficiency, governance practices, and external economic conditions. For Tier 3 commercial banks, this underscores the importance of diversifying strategies beyond risk management to improve financial outcomes. Managers should focus on improving internal processes, customer service, and product innovation while also addressing external challenges like market competition and regulatory compliance. Future studies should consider integrating broader variables, such as macroeconomic indicators or non-financial risk factors, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the drivers of financial performance in Tier 3 banks.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The analysis reveals that financial risks have a positive but insignificant relationship with the financial performance of Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya. This indicates that while managing financial risks might contribute to improved performance, the relationship is not strong enough to be considered impactful. It suggests that other factors have a more substantial influence on the financial performance of these banks. Moreover, it is recommended that Tier 3 commercial banks in Kenya adopt a more robust and integrated risk management framework to enhance their financial performance. This framework should prioritize proactive identification, assessment, and mitigation of financial risks, including credit, market, and liquidity risks, to minimize their potential adverse effects. Additionally, banks should invest in advanced risk analysis tools and training for staff to improve decision-making capabilities. Collaborating with regulatory authorities to ensure compliance with risk management standards and fostering innovation in financial products and services can also help improve competitiveness and resilience in a dynamic banking environment.

Acknowledgement

I dedicate this work to my family, whose unwavering support and encouragement have been my greatest motivation, and to my spouse, Dr. James Nganaga, for standing by me throughout this journey. I am profoundly grateful to the Almighty God for His guidance, strength, and provision during my studies. I extend my sincere gratitude to my supervisors, Prof. Gregory Namusonge and Prof. Romanus Odhiambo, for their commitment to my success, and to the Kenyan Public Universities Management and classmates whose insights and support have been invaluable to the completion of this work.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interests

References

- Aburime, T. U. (2015). Determinants of bank profitability: Macroeconomic evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of the University of Nigeria*, 1–31.
- Al Tamimi, H., & Al-Mazrooei, D. (2014). Factors influencing performance of the UAE Islamic and conventional national banks. *Journal of Finance & Economics*.
- Allen, G., & Galle, D. (2015). Financial intermediaries and markets. *Econometrica*, 72, 1023–1061.
- Angbazo, L. (2016). Commercial bank net interest margins, default risk, interest rate risk and off-balance sheet banking. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 21, 55–87.
- Asongu, S., & Asongu, N. (2018). The comparative exploration of mobile money services in inclusive development. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 45(1), 124–139. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-05-2016-0135>
- Badola, B. S., & Verma, R. (2015). Determinants of profitability of banks in India: A multivariate analysis. *Delhi Business Review*, 4(1), 89–93.
- Baele, L., De Jonghe, O., & Vennet, R. V. (2015). Does the stock market value bank

- diversification? *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 31(7), 1999–2023.
- Bagozzi, R. P. (1994). The effects of arousal on the organization of positive and negative affect and cognitions: Application to attitude theory. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 1, 222–252.
- Beaver, P. (2015). The association between market-determined and accounting-determined risk measures. *The Accounting Review*, 45(4), 654–682.
- Benton, E. G., & James, W. K. (2015). *Commercial banking: The management of risk* (3rd ed.). London: John Wiley & Sons.
- Bessembinder, H. (2016). Forward contracts and firm value: Investment incentive and contracting effects. *Business-Managerial Economics Research Centre*, 5(2), 1344–1356.
- Biryomumeisho, et al. (2017). Financial innovation and financial performance in financial institutions in Uganda. *Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 4(2), 94–104.
- Boyd, J. H., & Prescott, E. C. (2015). Financial intermediary coalitions. *Journal of Economic Theory*, 38(2), 211–232.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business research methods*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Carter, S., Vos, E., Yeh, A. J., & Tagg, S. (2015). The happy story of small business financing. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 31(9), 2648–2672.
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2010). *Annual bank supervision report*. Nairobi: Central Bank.
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2013). *Banking report*. Nairobi: Central Bank of Kenya.
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2016). Commercial banks and mortgage finance institutions. Retrieved from <https://www.centralbank.go.ke/index.php/bank-supervision/commercialbanks-mortgage-finance-institutions>.
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2017). Directory of commercial banks and mortgage. Retrieved from <http://www.centralbank.go.ke/downloads/bsd/CommercialBanksDirectory-04-January-2017>.
- Central Bank of Kenya. (2017). Quarterly report on development in the Kenyan banking sector for the period ended 30th June 2016. Retrieved from <http://www.centralbank.go.ke/downloads>.
- Chiarozza, W., Mlachila, M., & Tembo, T. (2014). Financial reforms and interest rates spreads in the commercial banking system in Malawi. *Journal of the International Monetary Fund*, 51(1), 96–122.
- Claessens, S., & Horen, N. (2012). Being a foreigner among domestic banks: Asset or liability? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 36(5), 1276–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2011.11.014>
- Cochran, W. G. (1963). *Sampling techniques* (2nd ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Cooper, R., & Schindler, S. (2013). *Business research methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Davis, F. D. (1993). User acceptance of information technology: System characteristics, user perceptions, and behavioral impacts. *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 38(3), 475–487. <https://doi.org/10.1006/imms.1993.1022>
- De Young, R., & Rice, T. (2015). Non-interest income and financial performance at USA commercial banks. *The Financial Review*, 39(1), 456–478.
- Dey, R. K., Syed, Z. H., & Zabihollah, R. (2018). Financial risk disclosure and financial attributes among publicly traded manufacturing companies: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm11020029>
- Diamond, D., & Dybvig, P. (2015). Bank runs, liquidity, and deposit insurance. *Journal of Political Economy*, 91, 401–419.
- Diamond, W. D., & Rajan, F. (2015). Liquidity and liability balance. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 2(3), 678–680.
- Donovan, K. (2012). Mobile money for financial inclusion. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Publication. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607–610.

- Eken, O., Memmel, C., Ruprecht, B., & Wilkens, M. (2015). Determinants of bank interest margins: Impacts of maturity transformation (Discussion Paper No. 17). Deutsche Bundesbank EuroSystem. Bonn: BundesBank.
- Eric, D. O., & Peter, A. (2016). Risk management and performance of listed banks in Ghana. *European Journal of Business Science and Technology*, 2(2), 107–121. <https://doi.org/10.11118/ejobsat.v2i2.63>
- Everitt, B. S. (2002). *The Cambridge dictionary of statistics* (2nd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Farhi, E., Tsyvinski, A., & Golosov, M. (2015). A theory of liquidity and regulation of financial intermediation (Working Paper No. 12959). *National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER)*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w12959>
- Gathikwa, C. (2011). The relationship between financial innovation and profitability of commercial banks in Kenya. Retrieved from <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/12516>
- Goddard, R. D., Hoy, W. K., & Hoy, A. W. (2012). Collective efficacy: A neglected construct in the study of schools and student achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 1(7), 7–12.
- Godfrey, F. (2015). Liquidity and bank performance for South African banks. *International Business & Economics Research Journal*, 14(3).
- Hirindu Kawshala. (2017). The factors affecting bank profitability in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(2).
- Holmstrom, B., & Tirole, J. (2015). Private and public supply of liquidity. *Journal of Political Economy*, 106, 1–40.
- Howells, P., & Bain, K. (2014). *The economics of money, banking and finance*. London: Prentice Hall.
- Hussaini, U. (2018). The effect of internal control on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Research & Review*, 8(6).
- Ignazio, V. (2014). Financial deepening & monetary policy transmission mechanism. *BIS Review*, 124. India: New Age International.
- Ishengoma, A. R. (2011). Analysis of mobile banking for financial inclusion in Tanzania: Case of Kibaha District Council. Retrieved from <https://www.econrsa.org>
- Jenkinson, N. (2016). Systematic risk in modern financial systems: Analytics and policy design. *Journal of Risk Finance*, 8(2), 45–50.
- Jensen, M., & Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)
- Kaiser, H. F. (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika*, 39, 31–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02291575>
- Kamau, M. (2016). Relationship between financial innovation and commercial bank performance in Kenya. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, 2(4).
- Kanika, M. (2012). Using mobile banking services to improve financial access for the poor: Lessons from Kenya, the Philippines, the United States, Haiti, and India. Retrieved from www.cgap.org/news/boost-mobile-banking-unbankedthrough-new-partnership
- Kappel, V. (2010). The effects of financial development on income inequality and poverty. *CER-ETH - Center of Economic Research at ETH*. Zurich: CER-ETH.
- Karimo, T. M., & Ogbonna, O. E. (2017). Financial deepening and economic growth nexus in Nigeria: Supply-leading or demand-following? *Economies*, 5(4), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies5040049>
- Kihuro, M. (2018). Credit risk management and bank performance: A critical literature review. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(6), Ver. IV (Nov. – Dec. 2018).
- Kithinji, A. M. (2010). Credit risk management and profitability of commercial banks in Kenya. (Unpublished master's thesis). University of Nairobi, Nairobi.

- Kithinji, A. M., & Waweru, N. M. (2007). Merger restructuring and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *Journal of Economics, Management and Financial Markets*, 2(4), 10–32.
- Kithinji, E. (2017). Effect of digital banking strategy on financial inclusion among commercial banks in Kenya. Retrieved from <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/102435/>
- Kithinji, M., & Waweru, M. (2015). Merger restructuring and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *Journal of Economics, Management and Financial Markets*, 2(4).
- Klein, M., & Mayer, C. (2011). Mobile banking and financial inclusion: The regulatory lessons. *Policy Research Working Paper No. 5664*.
- Koch, T. W., & MacDonald, S. S. (2002). *Bank management*. San Diego, CA: Hancourt.
- Kombo, D. K., & Tromp, D. L. A. (2010). *Proposal and thesis writing: An introduction*. Nairobi: Pauline's Publications Africa.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. Jaipur.
- Kothari, C. R., & Gang, W. (2014). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Ltd.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities.
- Lawrence, J. W. (2015). *Technological change, financial innovation and diffusion in banking*. New York: New York University.
- Love, I. (2003). Financial development and financing constraints: International evidence from the structural investment model. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 16(11), 765–791.
- Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G. (2015). Clarifying the entrepreneurial orientation construct and linking it to performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 21(1), 135–172.
- Mago, S., & Chitokwindo, S. (2014). The impact of mobile banking on financial inclusion in Zimbabwe: A case for Masvingo Province. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(9), 221–230.
- Makokha, A. N., Namusonge, G. S., & Sakwa, M. (2016). Effect of portfolio diversification on commercial banks financial performance in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 15(9), 5–8.
- Malakolunthu, S., & Rengasamy, N. C. (2012). Education policies and practices to address cultural diversity in Malaysia: Issues and challenges. *Prospects*, 42(2), 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-012-9227-9>
- Margrabe, K. (2007). The incidence of secured debt: Evidence from the small business community. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 24, 379–394.
- Marinković, S., & Radović, O. (2013). What determines credit growth in a small and open economy. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 26(sup2), 149–166.
- Markowitz, H. (1952). Portfolio selection. *The Journal of Finance*, 7(1), 77–91. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2975974>
- Marshall, S. A. (2009). Has mobile banking stimulated the financial sector? *Journal of Financial Innovations*, 2, 1–17.
- Meggie, T. W., & Gichinga, L. (2016). Factors influencing financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya: A case study of National Bank of Kenya Coast Region. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 1605(1), 34–50.
- Merritt, C. (2010). Mobile money transfer services: The next phase in the evolution in person-to-person payments. *Retail Payments Risk Forum White Paper*. Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, August 2010.
- Montiel, P. J. (2015). Financial policies and economic growth: Theory, evidence, and country-specific experience from Sub-Saharan Africa. *AERC Special Paper No. 18*. African Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. G. (2003). *Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Nairobi: ACTS Press.

- Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. G. (2009). *Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Nairobi: ACTS Press.
- Muiruri, S. (2014). Effects of financial innovations on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(7).
- Munjogu, J. N., & Namusonge, M. (2017). Influence of the adoption of mobile money payment strategy on organization performance of Nanyuki Water and Sewerage Company, Kenya. *European Journal of Business and Strategic Management*, 2(5), 1–15.
- Muriithi, J. (2017). Operational risk, bank size, and the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Financial and Banking Studies*, 6(3).
- Muteti, R. S. (2014). Relationship between financial risk management and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. (Unpublished master's thesis). University of Nairobi, Nairobi.
- Muthiora, A. (2015). KCB-SME Banking: Agribusiness. Retrieved from <http://images.agri-profocus.nl>
- Mutsonziwa, K., & Maposa, O. K. (2016). Mobile money - A catalyst for financial inclusion in developing economies: A case study of Zimbabwe using FinScope survey data. *International Journal of Financial Management*, 6(3), 45–56.
- Mutua, R. W. (2016). Effects of mobile banking on the financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Retrieved from <http://chss.uonbi.ac.ke/sites/default/files/chss/Rachael%20W%20Mutua%20Project.pdf>
- Mwania, B. (2016). An investigation on the relationship between information technology conceptualization and bank performance. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 23–34.
- Ndung'u, C. (2015). Determinants of commercial bank profitability in Kenya quoted banks. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 3(4), 34–45.
- Njihia, J. (2015). Determinants of bank profitability: The case of commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(1), 1–18.
- Noco, W., & Stulz, D. (2014). The economics of pension funds firms. *Journal of Pensions Schemes*, 4(444), 1098–1112.
- Noyer, C. (2007). Financial innovation, monetary policy and financial stability. Spring Conference, Banque de France.
- Noyer, C. (2015). Financial innovation, monetary policy and financial stability. Spring Conference of the Bank of France/Deutsche BundesBank. Eltville, Germany.
- Nyasaka, F. (2017). The relationship between credit risk management practices and non-performing loans in Kenyan commercial banks: A case study of KCB Group Limited. (Unpublished master's thesis). United States International University—Africa, Nairobi, Kenya.
- Obamuyi, T. M. (2007). An exploratory study of loan delinquency among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ondo State of Nigeria. *Labour and Management in Development*, 8, 2–8.
- Ogutu, M. (2019). Effect of e-banking on financial performance of listed commercial banks in Kenya. *Global Scientific Journal*, 7(1), January 2019.
- Okutoyi, R. (2015). The relationship between the use of strategic marketing and bank performance in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 1(2), 78–83.
- Ongore, V. O., & Kusa, G. B. (2016). Determinants of financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 3(1), 237–252.
- Otal, J. A., Aladesanmi, K. A., & Olufayo, M. B. (2014). Monetary policy and commercial banks performance in Nigeria: An assessment of credit creation role.
- Ouma, A., Odongo, T. M., & Were, M. (2017). Mobile financial services and financial inclusion: Is it a boon for savings mobilization? *Review of Development Finance*, 7(1), 29–35.

- Raza, R. O. (2015). Analysing the sources and impact of segmentation in the banking sector: A case study of Kenya. London: University of London.
- Riquet, C. (2013). Small farmers, mobile banking, financial inclusion in Madagascar. Retrieved from <http://www.cgiar.org/>
- Sandvik, A. (2015). Financial innovation, collateral and investment. *American Economic Journal*, 3, 242–284.
- Santiago, F., María, C. L., Carlos, L., Juan, C. R., & David, T. (2014). Financial inclusion and the role of mobile banking in Colombia: Developments and potential. Retrieved from <https://www.bbvaresearch.com/>
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2007). *Research Methods for Business Students* (4th ed.). Harlow: Prentice Hall Financial Times.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2013). *Research Methods for Business* (6th ed.). West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons.
- Senguder, Z., & Demirdjian, J. C. (2018). Regulation and bank performance in Tunisia.
- Shawn, C. (2016). Financial development, banking ownership, and growth: Does quantity imply quality? *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 91(1), 33–51.
- Siddik, M. N., Sun, G., Yanjuan, C., & Kabiraj, S. (2014). Financial inclusion through mobile banking: A case of Bangladesh. *Journal of Applied Finance and Banking*, 3(2), 34–46.
- Siddiqui, M. A. (2014). Towards determination of interest spread of commercial banks: Empirical evidences from Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5, 1851–1862.
- Smith, C. W., & Stulz, R. M. (2013). The determinants of firms' hedging policies. *The Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 3(8), 76–106.
- Sovan, M. (2010). Risk measures in quantitative finance. *International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management*, 3(2), 130–142.
- Staikouras, R. Y., & Wood, G. (2014). Income source diversification increases risk. *Journal of Banking Risk Management*, 34(2), 901–910.
- Stiroh, K. J. (2015). Diversification and banking: Is non-interest income the answer? *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 36(5), 853–882.
- Stiroh, K. J., & Rumble, A. (2015). The dark side of diversification: The case of U.S. financial holding companies. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 30, 2131–2161.
- Sufian, F., & Chong, R. R. (2014). Determinants of bank profitability in developing economies: Empirical evidence from the Philippines. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 3(4), 78–90.
- Teshale, B. (2011). Determinants of bank profitability: Evidence from selected Ethiopian commercial banks. *The Journal of American Business Review, Cambridge*, 6(2).
- The World Bank. (2017). Financial inclusion on the rise, but gaps remain: Global Findex database shows. Retrieved from www.worldbank.org/en/topic/financialinclusion
- Theuri, S. F., & Mwanjumwa. (2015). Factors influencing procurement performance in humanitarian relief organizations: A case of International Committee of the Red Cross in Kenya.
- Tufano, P. (2016). The consequences of financial innovation. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 7, 90–103.
- Ugoani, J. N. (2016). Non-performing loans portfolio and its effect on bank profitability in Nigeria. *Independent Journal of Management & Production*, 7(2), 302–319.
- Wilfred, C. (2006). Philosophy, methodology, and action research. *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, 40(4), 421–436.
- World Bank. (2016). Private provision of infrastructure database. *Journal of the World Bank*. Retrieved from <http://ppi.worldbank.org/about-us/about-ppi>